

Table 1 continued

Cultivar	Classification ^a					
	V20 A	V97 A	Pankhari 203 A	IR46826 A	IR54752 A	IR54753 A
Kalinga 3	PM	PR	PM	PR	PR	R
Dular	PR	PM	PM	PR	PM	R
Jaya	PM	PM	-	PM	PM	-
BG380-2	PR	PR	-	PR	PR	PR
BAU4045-2BI	PR	PR	PM	PR	PR	PM
BAU151-52	M	PM	PM	PR	PR	PM
NDR85	R	PM	PR	PM	R	PR
BAU148-28	R	PR	PR	PM	PR	PR
BAU148-30	PM	M	PM	PR	R	PM
ZHU XI-26	PR	PR	PM	PR	PR	M
IET7564	M	PM	PR	R	PM	R
Saket	PR	PM	-	R	PM	R
IET9789	R	PR	PR	PR	PR	-
IET9810	R	PR	PR	R	R	R
IET9815	R	R	PR	PR	PR	PR
VLK39	PR	PR	-	R	PR	PR
Sattari	PR	PR	-	PR	-	PR
Kalkari	PM	PR	-	-	M	PM
Neela	M	PR	PM	-	PR	PR
Sujata	PR	PR	PR	PR	-	PR
Archana	PR	PR	PR	PR	-	PR
RR51-1	PR	PR	-	R	PR	-
OR164-5	PR	PM	-	PM	PR	-
HPU734	PR	PM	PR	M	PR	-
IR50	R	R	-	-	-	-
IR88-30-3- 1-4-2	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
IR24594-204- 1-3-2-6-2	PM	PR	-	-	-	-
IR64	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
BG367-7	PR	R	-	-	-	-
Kalimeksi 77-5	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
IR62	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
SR4095-19-2-3-5-4	R	R	-	-	-	-
K438	R	PR	-	-	-	-
IR27078-3-6	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR19746-28-2-2-3	PM	PM	-	-	-	-
IR32093-B-1-B-23	PM	M	-	-	-	-
TKM6	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR912Y-KI	PR	PR	-	-	-	-
Tres Meses	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR29423-B-3-B-2-5-1	M	PM	-	-	-	-
S290	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
AC19-1-1	PM	PR	-	-	-	-
IR13155-60-3-1-3-1-1-3	M	PM	-	-	-	-
IR20897-B-6	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR29416-B-3-B-6-5-12	PR	PM	-	-	-	-
IR7790-18-1-2	PM	PR	-	-	-	-
IR28224-3-2-3-2	R	R	-	-	-	-

^aR = effective restorer, PR = partial restorer, PM = partial maintainer, M = effective maintainer.

Table 2. Isolation of maintainers and restorers of IR46828 A and IR54752 A.

Designation	Cross	Classification
TN8891	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₁	PR
TN8893	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₂	R
TN8895	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₃	PR
TN8897	IR46828 A/IR36 P ₄	R
TN8971	IR54752 A/IR35454-18-1-2-2-2 P ₁	R
TN8973	IR54752 A/IR35454-18-1-2-2-2 P ₂	PR
TN8983	IR54752 A/IR35293-178-2-3-1 P ₁	PR
TN8985	IR54752 A/IR35293-178-2-3-1 P ₂	R
TN9003	IR54752 A/IR28224-3-2-3-2 P ₁	R
TN9005	IR54752 A/IR28224-3-2-3-2 P ₂	PR
TN9015	IR54752 A/IR2307-247-2-2-3 P ₁	PR
TN9017	IR54152 A/IR2307-247-2-2-3 P ₂	R

biotic stresses. In addition, 23 more cultivars were crossed with V20 A and V97 A.

Pollen of each CMS line (tested by 1% iodine solution before crossing) was found to be highly sterile. The pollen parents and the F₁s were transplanted together to determine maintainers and restorers. Panicles were bagged before emergence.

On the basis of spikelet fertility, the cultivars were classified as effective restorer (>80% spikelet fertility), weak or partial restorer (40-79%), weak or partial maintainer (1-39%), and effective maintainer (<1%).

Effective restorers and maintainers for the CMS lines are in Table 1. IR46826 A, IR54752 A, and IR54753 A were found suitable for rainfed low-lands in the plateau region of Bihar.

Spikelet fertility was observed at IRR1 on F₁ progenies (10 plants each) of IR46828 A and IR54752 A and single plant selections of elite cultivars. Single plant selections of cultivars showed R to PR reaction (Table 2), indicating different restoring ability. It is necessary to purify cultivars for fertility restoration ability before using them in developing F₁ rice hybrids. ■

Yield potential

Seed dormancy of rice varieties released by Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University (APAU)

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Seed dormancy is needed in rice varieties grown during wet season (kharif) in AP coastal districts, which are prone to suffer cyclones and heavy rains at harvest.

We evaluated seed dormancy of all rice varieties released by APAU. Seed samples were collected 30 d after flowering and moisture content brought to 13-14% by sun drying. Dormancy duration (period required

Duration of dormancy of varieties released by APAU, India.

Variety with indicated dormancy					
1 wk	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	5 wk	6 wk
Puskala	Sowbhagya	Dhanya	Gowthami	Vasista	Gutti Akkulu
Hamsa	Prathibha	Lakshmi	Chaitanya	Kotha-	Kothamolokolukulu 72
Tella-Hamsa	Sona	Kakatiya	Vajram	Bayahunda	Kothamolokolukulu 74
	Mahsuri	Vamsi	Mahendra		
Rajendra	Pothana	Prabhath	Krishnaveni		Pinakini
Sathya	Saleema	Vijaya-Mahsuri			Tikkana
Badva		Nagavali			
Mahsuri		Lakshmi			
Mahsuri		Surekha			
		Samba -			
		Mahsuri			
		Swarna			

for 80% germination) was estimated by germination percentage.

Germination was tested weekly starting 1 wk after harvest, by sowing 100 seeds of each variety on a petri dish with four replications. Samples were maintained at a constant 30°C.

In general, long-duration varieties had longer seed dormancy (4-6 wk) than medium-duration varieties (2-3 wk) and short-duration varieties (1-2 wk) (see table). Exceptions are some long-duration varieties (Badva Mahsuri, Mahsuri, Sowbhagya, Prathibha, and Sona Mahsuri) that exhibited shorter dormancy (1-2 wk). ■

Effect of variety, nitrogen, and stubble height on ratoon rice yield

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Short-duration varieties ADT36, ASD16, and ADT37; N (75, 100, and 125 kg/ha), and 20- and 30-cm stubble height were tested in a split-plot design with three replications. The main crop followed recommended practices.

ADT37 had the highest ratoon crop grain yield, straw yield, and productive tillers and highest daily productivity (see table).

Nitrogen at 125 kg/ha gave significantly higher grain yield, straw yield,

Effect of variety, nitrogen, and stubble height on ratoon rice yield.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Days to maturity (no.)	Productivity (kg/d)
ADT36	2.5	2.5	8.7	77.4	32.3
ADT37	2.8	2.6	10.2	76.5	36.6
ASD16	2.2	2.3	8.5	89.4	24.6
LSD	0.1	0.1	1.2	2.3	-
75 kg N/ha	2.4	2.4	8.8	80.2	29.9
100 kg N/ha	2.5	2.5	9.1	81.1	30.8
125 kg N/ha	2.7	2.5	9.4	82.1	32.9
LSD (0.5)	0.1	0.1	ns	2.3	-
20-cm stubble	2.5	2.4	9.2	81.3	30.8
30-cm stubble	2.5	2.5	9.1	80.9	30.9
LSD	ns	ns	ns	ns	-

and daily productivity than 75 kg N/ha.

Stubble height had no effect on ratoon yields and productive tillers.

The high grain yield in ADT37 could be due to greater number of productive tillers. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Resistance of some rice varieties to sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is an increasingly serious disease of rice in the Yangtze River Basin, especially hybrid rice. In the search for resistance genes to transfer into commercial

Reaction ^a of varieties to ShB during 1987-89 in China.

Cultivar	Disease ratings (mean and SD) ^b			Average ^a
	1987	1988	1989	
Ta-poo-cho-z	1.43±0.389	0.46±0.190	1.35±0.293	1.08 a
Tetep	2.05±0.315	0.57±0.157	1.65±0.245	1.19 a
Guyanal	1.19±0.304	1.72±0.198	1.93±0.305	1.61 a
IET4699	2.47±0.249	0.49±0.153	2.53±0.233	1.72 ab
Ratna	1.92±0.283	0.98±0.222	2.58±0.287	1.83 ab
Jawa no. 14	2.51±0.214	0.74±0.153	2.50±0.292	1.93 ab
IR64	2.47±0.294	1.01±0.282	2.35±0.201	1.94 ab
Kataktara Da-2	2.9 ±0.206	0.96±0.240	2.51±0.180	2.12 ab
Mian-Hua-Tiao	2.96±0.227	1.58±0.218	2.90±0.200	2.48 ab
Ye-Dao	2.91±0.224	1.90±0.255	3.15±0.275	2.65 ab
P5275	2.85±0.304	2.16±0.335	3.01±0.401	2.67 ab
Nampungbyeo	2.78±0.316	2.15±0.279	3.21±0.248	2.71 ab
IR9752-71-3-2	4.24±0.411	3.76±0.327	4.56±0.309	4.22 b

^a 0 = no lesion, 5 = lesions extend to top sheath. ^b Mean of 10 random hills/treatment with 2 replications. ^c Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by new Duncan's multiple range test at the 1% level.